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History of the development of dance sports

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Abstract.

This article examines the history of the development of dance sports in Ukraine and the world, considers dance sports as a combination of sports and art; the impact of dancing on the physical development and psycho-emotional state of a person was investigated; the impact of dance on culture was analyzed, and the directions of the development of dance sports in Ukraine and the world were predicted.

Keywords:

*dance sport
competition
competitive program
personality development*

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Formulation of the problem. Dance sport is a unique combination of sport and art. Dance classes have a comprehensive impact on personality development and provide an opportunity to become physically and spiritually perfect. With the help of dance, you can express yourself and convey your mood and feelings, you can even change your life. Dance sport has no age limits and gives a feeling of harmony, lightness and beauty.

That is why the study of the historical development of dance sports in Ukraine and in the world is relevant.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Studying the characteristics of dance sports, it was established that dance sports are ballroom dances that are practiced professionally. The competitive sports dance program is divided into European and Latin American, which includes 10 dances. The European program includes: slow and Viennese waltz, tango, slow foxtrot, quickstep. In the Latin American program: cha-cha-cha, samba, rumba, pasadoble, jive [1, 2, 11, 13].

Well-known scientists T. Osadtsiv (2018), T. Pavlyuk (2020) in their works define in detail the directions and types of ballroom dances [7, 8]. Competitive dance sports in Ukraine are supported by the **All-Ukrainian Dance Sports Federation** (ADSF) and the **Sports Dance Association of Ukraine** (SDAU) [1, 2, 3, 7, 13].

The problem of the historical development of dance sports in Ukraine and the world was considered by scientists L. Onyshchenko (2019), T. Osadtsiv (2018), V. Syzonenko (2022) and in their works came to the conclusion that ballroom dancing originates in the distant past from folk dances and reflect the cultural and historical reality of society [6, 7, 11].

The relationship between ballroom dancing and the development of culture was studied by such Ukrainian scientists as: K. Sytchenko (2020), T. Osadtsiv (2018), O. Plohotniuk (2018), B. Hrynash (2022), T. Pavlyuk (2020) [4, 7, 8, 10, 12].

In her scientific work, L. Shestopal (2022) comprehensively analyzed the latest scientific research and came to the conclusion that ballroom dancing is an artistic

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and sociocultural phenomenon that needs to be studied [14]. The influence of dancing on the psycho-emotional state of the individual and its physical form is described in the works of Ya. Reva (2022), O. Lavrentiev (2022) [5, 9].

The author Ya. Reva (2022), in his scientific work, proves that dance has the widest range of educational, ethical, aesthetic, health-improving effects on the individual [9].

Thus, the analysis of the latest research on this issue makes it clear that the history of dance sports originates in the distant past, and the topic of the history of sports ballroom dancing and its development in the modern world is considered by Ukrainian scientists to be relevant for study.

Purpose: to investigate the development of dance sports from the beginning to the present.

Task:

1. To study the history of the development of dance sports in Ukraine and the world.

2. Consider dance sports as a combination of sports and art and analyze its influence on modern culture.

3. To study the influence of dances on the physical development and psycho-emotional state of a person.

4. To predict the directions of development of dance sports in Ukraine and the world.

Presentation of the main material. Dance is the art of "writing with movement", because since ancient times it has been a way of communication and an opportunity to express one's emotions. T. Osadtsiv (2018) wrote: "Ballroom dance is a historical phenomenon that goes back to everyday forms of folk dance" [7]. The beginning of the historical development of ballroom dancing can be considered the 17th century, when King Louis XIV of France founded the Royal Academy of Music and Dance.

Only in the 20th century did ballroom dancing take on a form close to its modern form, based on European dance, which was breathed new life into by African and Latin American music and dance culture at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries. The vast majority of modern ballroom dances have African "roots", disguised by the technical treatment of the European dance school. In the 1920s, a special Ballroom Dance Council was established in England under the Imperial Society of Dance

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Teachers. English specialists standardized all the dances known at that time - waltz, fast and slow foxtrot, tango. This is how competitive dances arose, and since then, ballroom dancing has been divided into two directions - sports and "social dance". The first Blackpool Dance Festival started in 1920 in the Winter Gardens in Blackpool and is still one of the most prestigious dance tournaments held in England. Officially, the first international amateur organization was created in 1935, it was named **Federation International Dancers Amateur** (FIDA).

From the moment of its creation, FIDA developed a booming activity and in 1936 the first official World Ballroom Dancing Championship was held in Berlin. In the modern world, ballroom dancing is both a way of entertainment and a sport, divided into European and Latin American programs (Table 1).

Table 1

Content of European and Latin American competition programs*

Competitive programs	
European	Latin American
slow waltz (boston)	samba
quickstep (quick foxtrot)	cha cha cha
Viennese Waltz	rumba
tango	pasodobl
slow foxtrot	jive

*- the table was created by the authors based on literary sources 1, 2 and 13.

This sport in our country is taken care of by ADSF and SDAU. ASTU was created and officially registered in 1985 in Lviv and is a member **International Dance Sport Association** (IDSA) and **European Dance Sport Federation** (EDSF) [1].

Ballroom dance competitions are held for amateurs and professionals and have different statuses and ranks: tournaments, cups, championships, club competitions, championships and festivals. Competitions of the highest level are held with the support of international organizations: the World Dance Council and the International Sports Dance Federation.

In sports ballroom dancing, a class system has been introduced, which reflects the level of training of dancers,

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as well as a system of age categories. To enter the first competition, dancers are assigned one of the lowest classes (H), which they can later change to a higher one. The highest class of mastery of M class dancers. Classification of dancers by training level: E class (6 dances); D class (8 dances); Class C (10 dances) – this class usually begins the serious career of dancers, followed by classes: B, A, S and M [13].

Classification of dancers by age groups: "children – 0", where the older partner is up to 6 years old inclusive; "children 1" – 7-9 years old; "children 2" – 10-11 years old; "juniors 1" – 12-13 years old; "juniors 2" – 14-15 years old; "youth" – 16-18 years old; "adults" – 19-34 years old; "seniors 1" – 35-44 years old; "seniors 2" – from 45 years old [13].

Classification of dancers by age groups: "children – 0", where the older partner is up to 6 years old inclusive; "children 1" – 7-9 years old; "children 2" – 10-11 years old; "juniors 1" – 12-13 years old; "juniors 2" – 14-15 years old; "youth" – 16-18 years old; "adults" – 19-34 years old; "seniors 1" – 35-44 years old; "seniors 2" – from 45 years old [13].

Ya. Reva (2022) in her scientific work analyzed the impact of ballroom dancing on the psycho-emotional state of a person and proved the possibility of using dance therapy as a method of psychological correction, development of creative potential and comprehensive improvement of the human body [9].

Thus, with the development of culture, dance gradually became part of important social events and an element of education and personal development, as well as a graceful and useful sport. Dance sport is an artistic, spectacular sport that reveals individual abilities and has a healing therapeutic effect on human health as a whole.

Conclusions:

1. During the study of the history of the development of dance sports, it was established that sports ballroom dances reflect the culture and art of different historical eras and peoples; and also represent a unique combination of art and sports, which comprehensively affects the development of personality and the formation of a creative cultural

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environment.

2. Dance sports, as an integration of art, culture and sports, with its multifaceted impact on the individual, needs further study, and will continue to be an important and integral part of society's life.

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